

BIOLOGY OF BER FRUIT FLY *CARPOMYIA VESUVIANA* COSTA

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ABSTRACT

Biology, incidence and morphometrics of the ber fruit fly *Carpomyia vesuviana* Costa were studied on Indian jujube *Ziziphus mauritiana* Lamark. The observations revealed that the female laid its eggs in the cavities made by the ovipositor, just beneath the skin of the fruit. The eggs were small, elongate, spindle shaped and creamy white. The duration of lifestages (in days) were- egg 1.90, maggot 8.75, prepupal 4.43 (hr), pupal 8.40, adult longevity 13.85; with a total lifecycle of 29.95 days. The length, width and wing expanse of female measured up to 4.82, 1.33 and 3.91 mm, respectively; and that of male 4.44, 1.21 and 3.83 mm, respectively. The incidence was maximum in October followed by December, with the least being in January. Correlation coefficients of incidence with weather factors revealed a significant and positive one with maximum RH (0.70) and negative with maximum temperature (-0.54).

Key words: *Carpomyia vesuviana*, *Ziziphus mauritiana*, biology, life stages, incidence, morphometrics, duration, population dynamics, temperature, relative humidity

The ber (*Ziziphus mauritiana* Lamark) also called as desert apple, jujube, Chinese apple, Kul or Boroi, Ber (Hindi), Indian plum and Permseret (Anguilla) is a tropical fruit tree species, belonging to the family *Rhamnaceae* (Balikai et al., 2013). Balikai (2009) reported a total of 22 insect and non-insect pests on ber, while Kavitha and Savithri (2002) about 23 pests. However, pests such as fruit fly *Carpomyia vesuviana* Costa, *Meridarchis scyroides* Meyr, chafer beetle, *Holotrichia consanguine* Blanch and bark eating caterpillar, *Indarbela tetraonis* Moore; *I. quadrinotata* Walker; ber butterfly, *Tarucus theophrastus* F. and stone weevil, *Aubeus himalayanus* Voss are the major ones (Sharma and Bal, 2009; Karuppaiah et al., 2015; Haldhar et al., 2016a). The grey weevil, *Mylocherus dentifer* (F.), *M. blandus* Faust, *Amblyrrhinus poricollis* Schoenherr; leaf webber, *Synclera univocolis*; ber mite, *Larvacarus transitans*, bark eating caterpillar, *Indarbela* sp. and termite, *Odontotermes* sp were recorded as minor pests (Haldhar et al., 2012; 2016b).

Fruit fly, *Carpomyia vesuviana* Costa (Diptera: Tephritidae) is the most destructive pest of ber in India. It is monophagous and infests only *Zizyphus* spp., causing low yield and poor quality of fruits (Haldhar et al., 2012; 2013; 2016). The fruit fly causes loss up to 80% (Batra, 1953). The brownish yellow adult flies emerge from the soil and start to infest ber fruits at

pea-size stage. Adults insert the eggs on the young developing fruits by making puncture with small cavity using protrusive ovipositor just below the epidermis of the immature fruits (Lakra and Singh, 1983; Dashad et al., 1999). Thus, newly emerged maggots feed on the pulp and making the galleries with accumulated excreta. In severe case, infestation may cause the fruit deformation and finally result in fruit drop (Lakra and Singh, 1983). This study explores the biology, incidence and morphometrics *C. vesuviana* on *Z. mauritiana*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Twenty fruits were randomly selected with three replications, and incidence observed as % during 2017-18 and 2018-19 in the entomological experimental field of ICAR-Central Institute for Arid Horticulture, Bikaner (N28°06'E73°21'). The maggots collected were brought to laboratory for observations, and the biology studied during October to December. These were reared in glass jars with fresh ber fruits. The male and female obtained were released in cages for egg laying. The adults were provided with 10% honey solution in cotton swabs that were left suspended in the cages throughout the period of egg laying in which fruits were placed in conical flasks (28± 2°C). Ten samples (egg, maggot stages, pupa and adult) were used for observation and measurements. The maggots were reared under laboratory condition

for measurements, and the measurements of body parts of male and female adults made in a stereozoom microscope (Radical Instruments, Ambala, Haryana) using Jenoptic Pro 2.8.0 software. The terminology used follows earlier work (Haldhar, 2012; 2015). Data were subjected to transformations before analysis for one-way ANOVA using SPSS software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results on the biology, incidence and morphometrics *C. vesuviana* are given in Table 1. The pooled data revealed that the female laid the eggs in the cavities made with protractible ovipositor just beneath the skin of the fruit. Usually two, but occasionally one egg was found in a cavity. The eggs were small, elongate, spindle shaped and creamy white, with hatching being 85%. The incubation period varied from 1.25 to 2.75 days with a mean of 1.90 days. The mean length and width of egg measured 0.86 mm and 0.20 mm, respectively. At the beginning, maggot was creamy white, started feeding on pulp, measuring 1.17 x 0.44 mm; while on the fourth day, it measured 4.85x 1.15 mm,

reaching its final instar in eight days. Full grown maggot measured 7.72x 1.50 mm, with the maggot period being 7.75 to 9.75 days. Bhagdavadze (1977) reported that female laid eggs in the slits of fruits, and was observed mostly during afternoons. This is in conformity with findings of Basha (1952). Kavitharaghavan et al. (2005) reported that egg hatching was 90%. The incubation period was 1.9 days, and length and width were 0.88 mm and 0.23 mm, respectively. Lakra and Singh (1986) observed that the egg stage was 1 to 4 days with the viability of 70.21 to 94.44%, and the larval period was 7 to 24 days and prepupal stage was 3 to 8 hr.

The damage observed from October to March revealed that the peak incidence was in October followed by December, with the least being during January (Fig. 1). The relationship between incidence and maximum temperature (-0.54) was negatively correlated whereas the maximum relative humidity (0.70) was positively correlated (Fig. 2; Table 2). Variation in the damage intensity occurs due to factors like rainfall, relative humidity and temperature (Lakra and Singh, 1985). In the central part of India (Gujarat)

Table 1. Biology and morphometrics of *C. vesuviana* (n=10)

S. No.	Life stages	Duration in days		
		X± SEM in 2017-18	X± SEM in 2018-19	X± SEM of Pooled data
1	Incubation period	1.85± 0.18	1.95± 0.16	1.90± 0.15
2	Maggot period	8.60± 0.16	8.90± 0.23	8.75± 0.19
3	Pre-pupal period (hours)	4.30± 0.24	4.55± 0.25	4.43± 0.24
4	Pupal period	8.30± 0.24	8.50± 0.25	8.40± 0.24
5	Pre oviposition period	3.65± 0.20	4.00± 0.18	3.83± 0.18
6	Oviposition period	7.00± 0.26	7.25± 0.26	7.13± 0.25
7	Adult longevity	13.75± 0.26	13.95± 0.28	13.85± 0.27
8	Total life cycle (From egg to adult emergence)	29.60± 1.11	30.30± 1.18	29.95± 1.13

Morphometrics

S. No.	Life stages	Length (mm)	Width (mm)
		X± SEM	X± SEM
1	Egg	0.86± 0.06	0.20± 0.01
2	Maggot immediately after hatching	1.17± 0.02	0.44± 0.01
3	Maggot at fourth day after hatching	4.85± 0.08	1.15± 0.02
4	Maggot at eight day after hatching	7.72± 0.02	1.50± 0.09
5	Pre pupa	7.59± 0.02	1.67± 0.01
6	Pupa	4.02± 0.05	1.69± 0.04
7	Female adult	4.82± 0.06	1.33± 0.02
8	Female adult wing expanse	-	3.91± 0.07
9	Male adult	4.44± 0.09	1.21± 0.02
10	Male adult wing expanse	-	3.83± 0.05

Mean values of ten samples

Fig. 1. Seasonal incidence of *C. vesuviana* in ber

the infestation started around mid October and increased suddenly in mid- November, and continued till December (Bagle, 1992). In Karnataka, in *Z. mauritiana* the activity of *C. vesuviana* was observed from December to February (Nandihalli et al., 1996). The soil physical factors like moisture, temperature and depth play a crucial role in the adult emergence from soil. The optimum temperature for pupal development was 30°C leading to maximum adult emergence (74%) and 3 to 6 cm pupation depth was ideal (Sangwan and Lakra, 1992). Temperature >40°C and low relative humidity <20 to 30% was unfavorable and prolonged immature stages occur beyond 5°C. The intermittent light rainfall ranging from 20 to 40 mm also promotes fly activity and moderate and heavy rainfall, 50 to 120 mm/ week curtails the activity (Lakra and Singh, 1983).

The maggots move towards the skin of the fruit making a circular hole on skin, come out of the fruit from these circular holes and fall into the ground for pupation. After fall on to the ground, maggot attached a inactive prepupal stage and entered slowly into soil by means of wriggling movement of the body. The prepupal stage was 4.43 hr, initially pupa was creamy white, and later turned brown. The pupa measured was 4.02x 1.69 mm, with a pupal period of 8.4 days (Table 1). The adult was a brownish yellow, with a brown longitudinal line on dorsal, ventral and pleural surfaces of the thorax. The adults length and width (female and male, respectively) measured 4.82, 1.33 and 4.44, 1.21 mm. The adult longevity was 13.85 days, with total lifecycle being 29.95 days.

Joshi and Shinde (1971) reported that in early stage of the fruit, generally a single egg was laid but in later stage, it goes up to 20, with bigger fruits being preferred. A minute brownish spot appeared at the site of puncture, with a total of 14.4 eggs/ female. The longevity under caged conditions ranged from 13 to 15 days. The male to female ratio was 1: 0.69. Kavitharaghavan et al. (2005) observed that length and width of maggot immediately after hatching was 1.2 and 0.45 mm, respectively.

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